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To the Pr Laurence Rothman, Editor of the Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfert

Créteil the 6th of May 2008,

Dear Professor,

Please find here enclosed our paper “Some improvements of the HNO₃ spectroscopic parameters in the spectral region from 600 to 950 cm⁻¹”, by L. Gomez, H. Tran, A. Perrin, R. R. Gamache, A. Laraia, J. Orphal, P. Chelin, C. E. Fellows, J.-M. Hartmann, that we would like to publish in the Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfert

Thank you in advance

Best wishes

Agnès Perrin

Some improvements of the HNO₃ spectroscopic parameters in the spectral region from 600 to 950 cm⁻¹

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Abstract:

- In an earlier study [Flaud JM, Brizzi G, Carlotti M, Perrin A, Ridolfi M, Atmos Chem Phys 2006; 6: 1-12] the HNO₃ line parameters in the HITRAN spectroscopic database have recently been revisited in the spectral range corresponding to the MIPAS spectral range. For the 11.3 μm, these updates involve the line positions for the {ν₅, 2ν₉} bands, and the intensities. However, comparisons between observed spectra recorded by MIPAS and the calculated ones in the 600-950 cm⁻¹ region, still show significant disagreements. The goal of the present paper is to solve some of these problems. Based on the analysis of N₂-broadened HNO₃ laboratory spectra recorded with a Fourier transform instrument, a new HNO₃ database was generated, including the following improvements: (i) Approximate parameters for the ν₅+ν₇-ν₇ and ν₅+ν₆-ν₆ hot bands have been added, and (ii), the intensities for the ν₆ and ν₈ bands have been updated. (iii) The air-broadening and its temperature dependence, calculated using a semi-classical approach, have been added for each HNO₃ transition. (iv) Finally, line-mixing effects have been pointed out, particularly in the ν₅+ν₉-ν₉ Q branch, and an approach correctly modeling the resulting spectral shape is proposed.

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1. Introduction

Nitric acid plays an important role in atmospheric chemistry since it acts as a reservoir of NO_x which are directly involved in ozone destruction [1]. HNO_3 is detected in operational mode by the "Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding" (MIPAS) on board the EnviSat satellite [2], for instance. The 11.3 μm region is widely used for the remote sensing of vertical distribution of HNO_3 [3-5] since it is located in an atmospheric window and contains strong absorption bands, namely the ν_5 and $2\nu_9$ cold bands located at 879 and 896 cm^{-1} together with the associated $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ and $3\nu_9-\nu_9$ first hot bands at 885 and 830 cm^{-1} [6].

In an earlier study [7] the HNO_3 spectroscopic parameters available in the HITRAN [8] and GEISA [9] databases have been revisited in the spectral region covered by MIPAS spectra. The line positions were improved in the 11.3 and 8.3 μm regions using new parameters determined in Refs. [10, 11]. The line intensities were also updated, mainly based on the integrated absorption cross sections measurements performed in the 820-5300 cm^{-1} region by Chackerian et al. [12]. Finally, the line broadening coefficients were also changed from the line independent values provided in the former versions of the data bases. The most accurate HNO_3 line broadening measurements were performed in the microwave or submillimeter spectral regions [13-18] where, contrary to the infrared, isolated lines can be observed. These measurements clearly evidence a rotational dependence of the air broadening coefficients. In the absence of accurate theoretical calculation at that time, it was decided to rely on a simple empirical model (see Ref. [19] for details) which reproduces as well as possible the measured values of the line broadening parameters.

For the 11.3 μm region (840-930 cm^{-1}), the residuals between atmospheric spectra recorded by MIPAS and those calculated using these new parameters [7] are considerably reduced when compared with results obtained using the previous line parameters available in HITRAN [8] or GEISA [20]. For this reason, these new parameters are now implemented in the updated version of the databases. However, when examining in details the results of these comparisons (see, for example, Figs. 1 and 2 of Ref. [7]) some significant features can be still observed in the residuals. The goal of the present paper is to further investigate nitric acid absorption in order to improve spectra calculations and correct for some of the observed discrepancies. For this purpose, several laboratory spectra of nitric acid broadened by N_2 (total pressures from 88 to 1019 hPa) have been recorded at room temperature using the Bruker IFS 125HR Fourier transform spectrometer of the LISA laboratory. These are used to

test the quality of the current spectroscopic list, first using Voigt line shapes. These comparisons evidence various discrepancies so that four modifications have been made in order to improve the [7] line list: (1) We have added line parameters for the $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ and $\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$ hot bands, which were not included in the previous line list. (2) The spectral range covered by the present study (600 to 950 cm^{-1}) includes the weak ν_6 and ν_8 bands. These bands which were not considered in the line intensity study performed in Ref. [12] were not updated in the new HITRAN and GEISA line list. From the present study we have observed that the intensities in HITRAN or GEISA for the ν_6 and ν_8 bands are not consistent with those of ν_5 and $2\nu_9$. More explicitly their intensities are overestimated by about 20-30%, and we thus propose values for these intensities. (3) Following recent line-broadening calculations [21] the air-broadening parameters were updated. (4) Finally, we propose a model for line-mixing effects in HNO_3 spectra. Its validity is demonstrated, particularly in the narrow Q branches of the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ and ν_8 bands which cannot be modeled at all pressures using Voigt isolated line shapes.

2. Experimental measurements

High-resolution infrared absorption spectra of HNO_3/N_2 mixtures were recorded using the Bruker IFS 125HR (an upgraded version of the IFS 120HR) Fourier-transform spectrometer (FTS) of LISA in Créteil. A glowbar source was used, together with a KBr beamsplitter with a dichroic coating and a MCT detector, in order to cover the 500-5200 cm^{-1} spectral range. The FTS was evacuated to about 0.05 hPa in order to reduce the absorption by laboratory air. Pressures were measured using calibrated MKS Baratron pressure transducers. The optical path difference used was 38 cm, leading to a spectral resolution of 0.013 cm^{-1} (boxcar apodization), and, for each HNO_3/N_2 mixture, 50 individual scans were recorded. This leads to a measurement time of about 20 minutes, short enough to make sure that the HNO_3 concentration in the absorption does not vary significantly between the first and last scans.

The White-type multipass absorption cell, made of pyrex glass and equipped with wedged CsI windows, was connected to the FTS with a dedicated optical interface (six mirrors) inside the sample chamber of the FTS. Its base length is of the 0.80 m, and, for the experiments described here, an optical path of 9.60 m was used, in order to work with low HNO_3 partial pressures and to eliminate any self-broadening effects.

In order to obtain a stable HNO₃ sample entirely free of NO₂ and of impurities due to previous measurements with the same cell, the later was first pacivated. For this purpose, the reaction of N₂O₅ with H₂O in the presence of O₃ was used. First, we introduced about 10 hPa of a mixture of 1% O₃ in O₂ (produced with a commercial discharge-based ozonizer, Sander Germany) into the absorption cell and allowed the mixture to stabilize during one night.

Second, we evacuated the absorption cell and filled it with about 0.2 hPa of pure NO₂ (Sigma Aldrich). Third, we added about 100 hPa of a mixture of O₃/O₂ which leads to the immediate production of N₂O₅ (through the reaction of NO₂ with O₃ producing NO₃ [22]), followed by the slow production of HNO₃ (by the heterogeneous reaction of N₂O₅ with residual H₂O on the walls of the absorption cell). All these reactions were monitored by recording low-resolution infrared absorption spectra. In order to complete the last reaction, the mixture was left in the absorption cell for another night. Finally, the total pressure in the absorption cell was reduced to about 5 hPa in order to achieve the desired HNO₃ absorption, and dry nitrogen (Air Liquide France) was added up to a total pressure of about 1 atm. The presence of some O₃ in the mixture guaranteed that any NO₂ produced from HNO₃ photolysis or decomposition would react back to NO₃ and then to HNO₃. Indeed, no residual NO₂ absorption is observed in the spectra.

Starting from the HNO₃/N₂ mixture, eight spectra were recorded at total pressures of 1019, 885, 754, 624, 489, 356, 223, and 88 hPa by progressively evacuating the cell. Before and after this procedure, spectra of the empty cell were recorded. Also note that the spectrum recorded with a high concentration of HNO₃ (after the filling of the cell with NO₂ and an O₃/O₂ mixture in the second step) allows for determination of the zero-transmittance baseline that can be slightly different from zero due to detector non-linearity. In addition we recorded an absorption spectrum of the HNO₃/O₂ mixture at a total pressure of 5 hPa, using a spectral resolution of 0.007 cm⁻¹.

3. Extended database and line-mixing model

3.1 Hot bands addition

Two (unidentified) Q-type structures located at 869.1 and 875.7 cm⁻¹ respectively are observed in our measured spectra. These wavenumbers correspond very closely to the differences between the measured positions of the $\nu_5+\nu_6$ (1521 cm⁻¹) and $\nu_5+\nu_7$ (1455 cm⁻¹)

bands [23] and the energies of the ν_6 (646.826 cm^{-1}) and ν_7 (580.304 cm^{-1}) levels [24]. We thus propose $\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$ and $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ for the assignments of the 869.1 and 875.7 cm^{-1} structures, respectively, since other possibilities can be eliminated. It is the case for the ν_5 and $2\nu_9$ bands of one of the minor isotopic variants of nitric acid. Indeed for the most abundant isotope variant H^{15}NO_3 , (with a relative abundance of 0.00364) ν_5 and $2\nu_9$ were already identified at 871.0955 and 893.4518 cm^{-1} , respectively [25], and the other isotopic variants are not abundant enough (0.0019 and 0.0003 for the isotopic variants in ^{18}O , and D respectively [26]) to be considered here. Other possible candidates for such assignments are hot bands of the main isotopic species. The rather strong $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ and the significantly weaker $3\nu_9-\nu_9$, first hot bands at 885 and 830 cm^{-1} , can be disregarded since they are already present in line lists (see Table 1). Finally, the $2\nu_9+\nu_x-\nu_x$ series of hot bands are expected to be considerably weaker than the $\nu_5+\nu_x-\nu_x$ first series. Indeed, as for $2\nu_9$, the $2\nu_9+\nu_x-\nu_x$ bands correspond to a difference of $\Delta\nu_9=\pm 2$ in the ν_9 vibrational quantum number, and these overtones transitions are expected to be very weak. However, one should mention that, in the particular case of H^{14}NO_3 , the $2\nu_9$ band is intense since it borrows most of its intensity from the strong ν_5 band. This is due to a Fermi type resonance between the 5^1 and 9^2 vibrational levels which is strong since the unperturbed vibrational states are very close in energy (only 7 cm^{-1} of separation) [11]. In principle, a similar Fermi resonance may also affect the $\nu_5+\nu_x$ and $2\nu_9+\nu_x$ states but it is expected to be weak due to the likely much larger energy separation between these levels. Finally, note that, as can be seen in Table 1, the $\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$ and $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ assignments are also consistent with intensity considerations. Indeed, since $E_7 < E_6$ the $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ band, having a more populated lower level, is stronger than the $\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$ one.

In the absence of high resolution data for the $\nu_5+\nu_6$ and $\nu_5+\nu_7$ bands, approximate line parameters for the two hot bands have been deduced from those of the ν_5 band. The position $\sigma_{\nu_5+\nu_x-\nu_x}(J, K_a, K_c \leftarrow J'', K_a'', K_c'')$ of a given transition of the $\nu_5+\nu_x-\nu_x$ ($x=6$ or 7) is deduced by applying a shift $-\delta_x$ to the position $\sigma_{\nu_5}(J, K_a, K_c \leftarrow J'', K_a'', K_c'')$ of the corresponding transition in ν_5 band, ie:

$$\sigma_{\nu_5+\nu_x-\nu_x}(J, K_a, K_c \leftarrow J'', K_a'', K_c'') = \sigma_{\nu_5}(J, K_a, K_c \leftarrow J'', K_a'', K_c'') - \delta_x, \quad (1)$$

with the values $\delta_6=10.0 (\pm 0.5) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\delta_7=3.4(\pm 0.2) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ determined from the measured spectra.

For an *isolated* bands, the intensity $S(v_n + v_x - v_x)$ of an individual rotational transition $v_n + v_x, J, K_a, K_c \leftarrow v_x, J'', K_a'', K_c''$ of the $v_n + v_x - v_x$ hot band can be approximated from the corresponding intensity $S(v_n)$ of the similar rotational transition $v_n, J, K_a, K_c \leftarrow \text{ground}, J'', K_a'', K_c''$ of the cold v_n band by simply applying a Boltzmann population factor, *ie*:

$$S(v_n + v_x - v_x) = S(v_n) \exp\left(\frac{-hcE_x}{k_B T}\right), \quad (2)$$

where h is the Planck constant, c is the light speed, E_x is the vibrational band center for the v_x band, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, and T the temperature. In the case of the $v_5 + v_6 - v_6$ and $v_5 + v_7 - v_7$ hot bands of H^{14}NO_3 , this expression must be modified. Indeed, through the $5^1 \leftrightarrow 9^2$ Fermi resonance, there is a partial transfer of intensity from the v_5 to the $2v_9$ band. In order to take this effect into account, the individual line intensities of the $v_5 + v_6 - v_6$ and $v_5 + v_7 - v_7$ transitions are written as:

$$S(v_5 + v_x - v_x) = S(v_5) \exp\left(\frac{-hcE_x}{k_B T}\right) f_x \quad (3)$$

with $x=6,7$. The f_6 and f_7 factors were adjusted on the observed spectra, leading to $f_6=1.4(\pm 0.2)$ and $f_7=1.6(\pm 0.2)$. These values are greater than unity since the $5^1 + x^1$ and $9^2 + x^1$ (unknown) vibrational states are (likely) further apart than 5^1 and 9^2 so that the transfer of intensities is weaker than for the cold bands.

Table 1 synthesizes the characteristics of the line lists which were generated for the $v_5 + v_6 - v_6$ and $v_5 + v_7 - v_7$ hot bands. Figure 1 displays two observed spectra and corresponding simulations performed with the original HITRAN line parameters available and with those of our new database including the $v_5 + v_6 - v_6$ and $v_5 + v_7 - v_7$ hot bands. It is clear that the quality of the simulation in the $869\text{-}876 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is significantly improved.

3.2 Calibration of the v_6 and v_8 bands intensities

Our measured spectra enable a test of the relative consistency of the HNO_3 line intensities in the whole $600\text{-}950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral region. In order to do this, the unknown HNO_3 amount in our experiments is determined from the absorption in the $11.3 \mu\text{m}$ region (*ie*, v_5 , $2v_9$, and associated hot bands). This is valid, since the associated line intensity parameters were recently accurately updated [7] by using the results of the exhaustive measurements of nitric acid integrated absorption cross sections performed in Ref. [12]. However, the low

frequency range 600-820 cm^{-1} , which is not covered by the measurements of Ref. [12] was not updated. For the ν_6 and ν_8 bands at 646.826 and 763.154 cm^{-1} , respectively, the line intensities presently available in HITRAN [27] have been scaled to the band intensity measurements of Ref. [28]. The question of the consistency of the line intensities is of relevance. It is further justified by the fact that, from Ref. [29], it was concluded that the ν_6 and ν_8 intensities in HITRAN database [27] are overestimated by a factor of about two. Finally note that the line positions were slightly improved in Refs. [30] and [31] for the P and R branches of the ν_6 and ν_8 bands, respectively, but not for the Q branches.

The inadequacy of the ν_6 and ν_8 intensities in HITRAN is confirmed by the present study where scaling factors (with respect to the HITRAN values) of 0.74 and 0.78 have been deduced for the ν_6 and ν_8 bands, respectively. This leads to significantly improved agreement with measured spectra, as shown in Figs. 2 and 3. Note that the two strong peaks in the residuals of Figure 2 are due to CO_2 lines of the ν_2 band (from small CO_2 impurities in the N_2 used for the experiments).

3.3 New line broadening parameters

New accurate γ_{air} air-broadening parameters for HNO_3 were introduced in our spectroscopic line list. They result from semi-classical calculations for $\text{HNO}_3\text{-N}_2$ performed by R.R. Gamache and co-workers following a method based on the complex Robert-Bonamy formalism. Details of these calculations can be found in Ref. [21]. The $\gamma_{\text{air}}/\gamma_{\text{N}_2} = 0.935$ ratio was estimated using the experimental values of γ_{N_2} and γ_{O_2} (O_2 -broadening parameters) of Refs. [13-17].

3.4 Line-mixing effects

At this step, we have built an improved (approximate) database for HNO_3 line parameters in the region from 600 to 950 cm^{-1} , which is more complete and precise than that of [7]. The remaining point studied here is line-mixing [32], which is restricted to the Q branches of strong bands since, in the pressure range considered, this process negligibly affects P and R branches. The approach used here is similar to that of Refs. [33, 34]. We assume the impact approximation and binary collisions and neglect Doppler effects since much smaller than the collisional broadening in the studied pressure range. The absorption

coefficient, α , in cm^{-1} , for HNO_3 perturbed by N_2 accounting for line-mixing effects at wavenumber σ and temperature T is then given by:

$$\alpha^{\text{LM}}(\sigma, P_{\text{HNO}_3}, P, T) = \frac{8\pi^3\sigma}{3hc} [1 - \exp(-hc\sigma/k_B T)] \times \frac{P_{\text{HNO}_3}}{k_B T} \times \frac{1}{\pi} \text{Im} \left\{ \sum_{\ell} \sum_{\ell'} \rho_{\ell}(T) d_{\ell} d_{\ell'} \langle \langle \ell' | [\Sigma - \mathbf{L}_0 - i\mathbf{P}\mathbf{W}(T)]^{-1} | \ell \rangle \rangle \right\}, \quad (4)$$

where the summation is over all ℓ and ℓ' absorption lines. P_{HNO_3} and P are respectively the HNO_3 partial pressure and the total pressures, P thus being the N_2 pressure since HNO_3 is highly diluted. Σ , \mathbf{L}_0 and \mathbf{W} are operators in the Liouville line space, ρ_{ℓ} is the relative population of the initial level of the line ℓ , d_{ℓ} is the matrix element of the electric dipole moment operator for line ℓ . The latter is related to the integrated intensity S_{ℓ} by the expression:

$$S_{\ell}(T) = \frac{8\pi^3}{3hc} \rho_{\ell}(T) \times \sigma_{\ell} \times [1 - \exp(-hc\sigma_{\ell}/k_B T)] \times d_{\ell}^2. \quad (5)$$

Σ and \mathbf{L}_0 are diagonal with elements related to the current wavenumber σ and the line positions σ_{ℓ} by:

$$\langle \langle \ell | \Sigma | \ell' \rangle \rangle = \sigma \times \delta_{\ell, \ell'}, \quad \langle \langle \ell | \mathbf{L}_0 | \ell' \rangle \rangle = \sigma_{\ell} \times \delta_{\ell, \ell'}. \quad (6)$$

\mathbf{W} is the relaxation operator which off-diagonal elements account for the interferences between absorption lines (line-mixing) whereas the real and imaginary parts of the diagonal ones are the collisional broadening and shifting coefficients, γ_{ℓ} and δ_{ℓ} , respectively, *ie*:

$$\langle \langle \ell | \mathbf{W}(T) | \ell \rangle \rangle = \gamma_{\ell}(T) - i\delta_{\ell}(T). \quad (7)$$

The pressure shifting coefficients, expected to be very small [18], are considered as negligible in the pressure range considered in this work and the entire imaginary part of \mathbf{W} is therefore

neglected. The real-valued off-diagonal elements are modeled using the state-to-state inelastic collisional rates of the lower states as:

$$\langle\langle \ell' | W(T) | \ell \rangle\rangle = -A_{\ell',\ell} \times K(i_{\ell'} \leftarrow i_{\ell}, T) \quad , \text{ with } (\ell' \neq \ell), \quad (8)$$

where $K(i_{\ell'} \leftarrow i_{\ell}, T)$ is the collisional transfer rate from the initial level i_{ℓ} of line ℓ to the initial level $i_{\ell'}$ of the line ℓ' . The empirical $A_{\ell',\ell}$ parameters which relate state-space to line-space quantities are empirical and depend, strictly speaking, on the lines considered. In order to simplify the problem, we assume that $A_{\ell',\ell}$ depends only on the type of the considered band. The downward rates $K(i_{\ell'} \leftarrow i_{\ell}, T)$, with $E_{\ell'} < E_{\ell}$ are modeled by an Exponential Power Gap fitting Law (EPGL) [34]

$$K(i_{\ell'} \leftarrow i_{\ell}, T) = a_1 \left(\frac{hc|E_{\ell} - E_{\ell'}|}{k_B T} \right)^{-a_2} \exp\left(-\frac{a_3 hc|E_{\ell} - E_{\ell'}|}{k_B T} \right), \quad (9)$$

The upward ones have been deduced from the following detailed balance relation:

$$K(i_{\ell} \leftarrow i_{\ell'}, T) = \frac{\rho_{\ell}(T)}{\rho_{\ell'}(T)} K(i_{\ell'} \leftarrow i_{\ell}, T), \quad (10)$$

The a_1 , a_2 and a_3 coefficients are obtained from least-squares fits of the collisional broadening coefficients γ_k using the following sum rule applied for a Q branch:

$$\gamma_{\ell} = \sum_{\ell' \neq \ell} K(i_{\ell'} \leftarrow i_{\ell}). \quad (11)$$

For the Q branches considered in this work (ν_5 , $2\nu_9$, $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$, ν_8), due to symmetry considerations, only rates connecting rotational levels with the selection rule ΔK_c odd, are non zero. Imposing this and using Eqs. (9)-(11) for a fit of line broadening values leads to the following parameters for the EPGL fitting law: $a_1 = 0.00117$, $a_2 = 0.015$, $a_3 = 13.95$ and to the results of Figure 4. The agreement is not perfect but still reasonable. The final parameters A of Eq. (8) have then been determined from fits of the experimental spectrum for $P=1019$ hPa. They are $A=0.5$ and $A=0.3$ for type A (ν_5 , $2\nu_9$, $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$) and type C (ν_8) bands, respectively.

As a first example, comparisons between measurements and calculations for the Q branch of the hot band $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ at different pressures are shown in Figure 5. As can be expected [32], Lorentzian lineshapes strongly underestimate peak absorption whereas overestimates the Q branch width. On the opposite, our model leads to significant improvement and satisfactory agreement, demonstrating that line-mixing must be accounted for in the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ Q branch. On the contrary, no appreciable line-mixing effects are detected

for the ν_5 and $2\nu_9$ Q branches since their lines are more widely spread [35, 11]. Finally, results obtained for the ν_8 Q branch are shown in Figure 6 where line-mixing effects are detected but are significantly weaker than that of the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ Q branch.

In order to simplify the practical inclusion of line-mixing effects in atmospheric computation codes, a simple approach is proposed. It consists in calculating the profiles of the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ and ν_8 Q branches using Lorentzian line shapes with ad-hoc broadening parameters. As can be observed in Figs. 5 and 6, the lines within $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ and ν_8 Q branches strongly overlap and the rotational structure vanishes even at low pressures. In this case, the Q branch shape is mainly governed by its equivalent broadening parameter [32] given by:

$$\bar{\gamma}_{\text{branch}}^{\text{LM}} = \text{Re} \left\{ \frac{\sum_{\ell, k \in \text{branch}} \rho_{\ell} d_k d_{\ell} W_{k\ell}}{\sum_{\ell \in \text{branch}} \rho_{\ell} d_{\ell}^2} \right\}, \quad (12)$$

Due to the off-diagonal real elements of \mathbf{W} , this broadening is smaller than that predicted by the isolated lines model. We can thus artificially reproduce line-mixing effects by using Lorentzian lineshapes where the line broadening coefficients are smaller than that of isolated lines. For this purpose, we have multiplied the line broadening coefficient by a factor smaller than unity, and it is determined by comparisons between observed and calculated spectra. For the ν_8 Q branch line, its value is of 0.77. For the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ Q branch lines, it is 0.66, not for all the lines in the branch but only for those belonging to the spectral interval from 885.40 to 885.45 cm^{-1} . In fact, as shown on Fig. 7, unlike the case of the ν_8 Q branch where lines attribution is regular as function of the wavenumber, in the case of the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ Q branch, lines outside this spectral region (885.40-885.45 cm^{-1}) are weak compared with the lines belonging to this interval and they are far enough to consider that they do not contribute appreciably to the line-mixing effect in the band. In order to prove the consistency of this approach, comparisons between measurements and calculations accounting for line-mixing effects using our model (Eqs. (4-11)) and using equivalent Lorentzian line shapes are shown at different pressures in Figure 8 for the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ Q branch. A similar result is obtained for the ν_8 Q branch.

Finally, in Figure 9 we show the spectrum measured at 885 hPa in the whole spectral region studied in this work and the differences between measured values and calculations obtained from HITRAN parameters and from our new database.

4. Conclusion

A new and improved HNO₃ database was generated by analyzing spectra of nitric acid broadened by N₂ recorded in the 600-950 cm⁻¹ region using the Bruker IFS 125 HR FTIR of the LISA laboratory. During this study, two hot bands $\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$ and $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ located at 869.1 and 875.7 cm⁻¹ were included in this new database. The intensities were updated for the ν_6 and ν_8 bands at 646.8 and 763.1 cm⁻¹ respectively. The line broadening parameters were updated using a new calculation. Also it was possible to identify, for the first time, and model correctly line mixing effects in the Q branch regions of the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ (at 885.425 cm⁻¹) and ν_8 (at 763.154 cm⁻¹) bands. These new parameters will improve the quality of the atmospheric spectra calculations and retrievals in the 10-16 μm region, as will be demonstrated in a forthcoming paper.

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TABLE CAPTIONS

Table 1. Summary of the HNO₃ bands on this new database.

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Absorption coefficients measured (\bullet) and calculated with (—) and without (---) the addition of the $\nu_5+\nu_6-\nu_6$ and $\nu_5+\nu_7-\nu_7$ hot bands for a temperature of 296 K and a total pressure of (a) 356 hPa, and (b) 1019 hPa. The curves in the lower layers are corresponding deviations (obs-calc).

Figure 2. Absorption coefficients measured (\bullet) and calculated multiplying (—) and not multiplying (---) the intensities of ν_6 band in HITRAN database by a factor of 0.74, for a temperature of 296 K and a total pressure of (a) 356 hPa, and (b) 1019 hPa. The curves in the lower layers are corresponding deviations (obs-calc).

Figure 3. Absorption coefficients measured (\bullet) and calculated multiplying (—) and not multiplying (---) the intensities of ν_8 band in HITRAN database by a factor of 0.78, for a temperature of 296 K and a total pressure of (a) 356 hPa, and (b) 1019 hPa. The curves in the lower layers are corresponding deviations (obs-calc)..

Figure 4. Q branch line broadening coefficients of HNO_3 perturbed by N_2 in function of J. The open symbols correspond to calculated values (see text) and the full symbols to PEGL fit (Eqs. (8-11)).

Figure 5. Absorption coefficients measured (\bullet) and calculated with (—) and without (---) line-mixing effects in the region of the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ hot band for a temperature of 296 K and a total pressure of (a) 356 hPa, (b) 754 hPa, and (c) 1019 hPa. The curves in the lower layers are corresponding deviations (obs-calc).

Figure 6. In the top: absorption measured in the region of the ν_8 band for a temperature of 296 K and a total pressure of (a) 754 hPa and (b) 1019 hPa. The curves in the medium and the lower layers are respectively the differences between measured spectra and calculations without and with line-mixing effects.

Figure 7. Intensities of the (a) $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ and (b) ν_8 Q branches lines deduced from our new database.

Figure 8. Same experimental conditions as in Fig. 3 but the comparisons are between measurements (black points) and calculation accounting for line-mixing effects using our model (grey line) and using equivalent Lorentzian lineshapes (black line). The (obs-calc) corresponding values are plotted in the lower layers. Differences between measurements and calculation without line-mixing effects (dash) are also reported for comparison.

Figure 9. Absorption of HNO_3 diluted in N_2 measured at 885 hPa and 296 K. Differences between measurement and calculation using (a) the old database and (b) our new data base are plotted in lower layers. Regions with improvements thanks to our new data base are shown by an arrow.

Band	Band Center (cm ⁻¹)	S _{TOT} (cm ⁻¹ /molc·cm ⁻²)	S _{min} (cm ⁻¹ /molc·cm ⁻²)	S _{max} (cm ⁻¹ /molc·cm ⁻²)	number of lines	σ _{min} (cm ⁻¹)	σ _{max} (cm ⁻¹)
v ₅	879.108	1.027 E-17	9.83 E-25	6.60 E-21	57108	806.207	963.995
v ₆	646.826	1.263 E-18	2.83 E-23	8.54 E-22	8379	615.026	677.981
v ₆	646.826	9.342 E-19	2.09 E-23	6.32 E-22	8379	615.026	677.981
(updated)							
v ₈	763.154	1.242 E-18	1.21 E-23	1.09 E-21	7101	722.533	809.965
v ₈	763.154	9.689 E-19	9.45 E-24	8.50 E-22	7101	722.533	809.965
(updated)							
2v ₉	896.447	7.503 E-18	9.83 E-25	3.88 E-21	55310	806.709	963.435
v ₅ +v ₆ -v ₆	869.1	6.179 E-19	5.92 E-26	3.97 E-22	57108	796.207	953.995
(new)							
v ₅ +v ₇ -v ₇	875.7	9.760 E-19	9.35 E-26	6.27 E-22	57108	802.807	960.595
(new)							
3v ₉ -v ₉	830.675	5.291 E-19	3.84 E-25	6.72 E-22	17720	769.687	884.438
v ₅ +v ₉ -v ₉	885.425	1.067 E-18	9.87 E-25	7.00 E-22	14521	832.117	942.901

Table 1.

Figure(s)

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